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2021 Southern California Gas Company Emission Factor Update

Distribution Main & Service Buried Leak Emission
Factors and Decision Tree Output Factors for Large Leak
Prioritization Screening Process

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Executive Summary

This report is part of an overall project to develop Company-Specific leak-based emissions factors for buried Distribution system leaks, and a Decision Tree methodology for identifying and differentiating leaks that have high flow leak rates characterized by a leak rate of 10 CFH or greater, for the purpose of prioritizing repairs and reducing natural gas emissions from the distribution system.

By reducing the number and duration of higher emitting non-hazardous leaks, actual emissions can be reduced and the approach for identifying and differentiating leaks is expected to result in a more accurate demonstration of emissions reductions. A preliminary analysis of the Decision Tree methodology was published in the August 21, 2020 GTI Report titled “2019 Emission Factor Pilot Study” [1] (known as Phase 1).

The objective of this study is to further refine the Decision Tree methodology for flagging large leaks through additional measurements collected in 2019 and 2020 (referred to as Phase 2). The Phase 2 data set added an additional 91 leak samples, raising the total sample size from 291 to 382 samples. In this report, a statistical analysis of the combined Phase 1 and Phase 2 data sets will be conducted and compared with the previous results in Phase 1.

This study conducted statistically sound sampling of non-hazardous pipeline leaks using well-proven field measurement techniques to provide data to calculate company-specific methane emission factors for Southern California Gas Company (SoCalGas) buried Distribution system leaks. State-of-the-art parametric and non-parametric statistical analysis, resampling, Monte Carlo, and Bayesian probabilistic analysis were used when appropriate.

The Decision Tree (DT) error true/false positive/negative rates improved with the addition Phase 2 data. For example, the true negative rate (i.e., the probability that a leak does not meet the DT criteria and is <10 SCFH) increased from 98.9% to 99.1% while the false positive rate (i.e., the probability that a leak meets the DT criteria and is > 10 SCFH) decreased from 89.7% to 86.6% false positive rate associated with predicted leak and actual leak rates.

Emission Factors (EFs) for the combined data set were derived using a combination of the appropriate bootstrap population leak rate means and the Bayesian Decision Tree error table percentiles (95% confidence) and only differed by approximately 2%-5% from the isolated Phase 1 data set. The additional random samples added from the Phase 2 effort showed excellent correlation and a slight refinement of the EFs.

SoCalGas started the system-wide implementation of a Large Leak Prioritization (LLP) process using the DT method in Q2 2020. Figure 1 below shows the planned LLP workflow process. Note that, for generating emission factors, the DT method utilizes a 10 SCFH threshold to separate large and non-large leaks; however, the LLP implementation process takes a more conservative approach by prioritizing any leak with a flow rate of 6 SCFH or greater for repair.

Figure 1: SCG Large Leak Prioritization Decision Tree including EF Assignments.

¹The normal repair cycle is based on leak grade (e.g., Haz leaks are repaired immediately, Non-Haz leaks are currently repaired within three years)

²The need for flow rate data is dependent on local operations' ability to accelerate the leak repair without a flow rate measurement. Measurement of leak flow rate is also dependent on operational issues; such as outskirt areas not resourced to perform leak flow rate measurements; Insufficient time prior to repair; and accessibility issues.

Introduction

This report summarizes the statistical analysis and results for data provided by Southern California Gas Company (SoCalGas) as a 2021 update for the SoCalGas Distribution Main & Service (DM&S) buried leak emission factors and Decision Tree (DT) output factors for the associated Large Leak Prioritization (LLP) screening process.

This report builds upon the Phase 1 work conducted and reported in the August 21, 2020 GTI Report prepared for OTD titled, "2019 Emission Factor Pilot Study"[1]; this is referred to as the *Phase 1* report and associated data set (291 samples) in the remainder of this document, which in turn analyzes follow on sampling termed the *Phase 2* data set (91 additional samples) and then combines Phase 1 and 2 data (382 total samples) to develop an updated set of emission factors.

The reader is directed to the Phase 1 report to gain further details in the background of the approach as well as the methodology developed and applied in both phases. The key background sections of the Phase 1 report listed directly below are all applicable to the methods and processes used in this report (referred to as Phase 2) and the updated Emission Factors, which is the focus of this report.

Phase 1 Report Key Background Sections

Background - Regulator, Industry Studies, and SoCalGas Process Development

- California Rule Making
- Leak Grading in California
- Summary of SoCalGas and Past Industry Studies Referenced or Developed as Part of Phase 1

Approach for Field Sampling, Measurement Techniques, and Decision Tree (DT) Process

SoCalGas Process Development

- Development of the Decision Tree Approach
- Selection of Single vs. Facility/Material Specific EFs
- Precision and Sample Size Analysis - Minimum Sample Size

Physical Sampling Plan - Where to Sample

Methodology Overview of Data Collection and Statistical/Probabilistic Analysis

- Descriptive Statistics of Study Samples
- Data Transformation, Regression, and MCMC Models
- Decision Tree Predictive Performance
- Population Mean Leak Rate Inferential Analysis
- Emission Factor Determination
- Method of Emission Factor Application
- Quality Assurance

The remainder of this report will provide an update of the SoCalGas DM&S leak rate data, Decision Tree leak prediction quantitative performance, population mean leak rate analysis, and the resulting updated emission factors all related to the SoCalGas buried DM&S system leaks.

Summary and Time Period of Data Sets Referenced or Developed as Part of this Report

SoCalGas collected field leak concentration measurements and leak flow rate data based on a geographically diverse, stratified random sample of the entire SoCalGas distribution system, which established a technically sound foundational leak flow rate dataset. A summary of the Phase 1 and 2 data sets included in this report are summarized in Table 1 below. This study was conducted from 2019 through 2021. This includes the development of the DT process and the Phase 1, Phase 2, and ongoing sample and data collections.

Table 1: Phase 1 and 2 Data Sets Used in this Report.

Sub-Study	Header/Legend Abbreviation	Year(s) Performed	Report Year	Scale	Number of Samples	Used for Report EFs	Reference Number
Data Sets Included in the Phase 1 Report							
SoCalGas Decision Tree 157 Pilot	DT157	2015-2019	2019	SoCalGas	157	Phase 1 & 2	
SoCalGas All District Sample	AllDis_P1	2019	2019	SoCalGas	78	Phase 1 & 2	[1]
SoCalGas 3-District Pilot	3Dis_P1	2019	2019	SoCalGas	56	Phase 1 & 2	
Phase 2 Data Sets Added to Phase 1 Data for this Report							
SoCalGas All District Sample	AllDis_P2	2020	2019	SoCalGas	59	Phase 2	
SoCalGas 3-District Pilot	3Dis_P2	2019 ⁽¹⁾ -2020	2019	SoCalGas	32	Phase 2	This Report
Total (Phase 1 & 2) Samples Used to Calculate the Revised Emission Factors in this Report					382		

(1) Three samples measured in Dec. 2019 from the 3-District Pilot area are part of the Phase 2 dataset. These samples were obtained after the 11/22/19 cut-off for the Phase 1 effort. The remaining 29 of 32 Phase 2 3-District Pilot and all 59 of the Phase 2 All District Study samples were measured between Jan. 1 to Dec. 31, 2020.

In this report, the term *Sub-Study* refers to the individual DT157 and separate Phase 1 and Phase 2 data sets from the 3-District and All District Studies. The term *Study* refers to the combined (i.e., rolled-up) Phase 1 & 2 3-District, Phase 1 & 2 All District, and DT157 studies.

The combined Phase 1 and 2 data sets are included in **Appendix A** of this report.

Analysis and Results of Updated Data Sets

Descriptive Statistics

The new data obtained from the Phase 2 data sets were quality checked and arranged into a single flat table along with the Phase 1 data. This data is included in **Appendix A** of this report. Sample counts as well as *methane* leak rate mean, minimum, and maximum for each of the five sub-studies are compiled in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Leak Rate Mean, Minimum, and Maximum by Sub-Study.

Sub-Study	N(count)	mean(scfh)	min(scfh)	max(scfh)
3Dis_P1	56	11.952	0.020	373.000
3Dis_P2	32	6.641	0.012	60.432
AllDis_P1	78	1.575	0.003	27.045
AllDis_P2	59	2.355	0.001	54.811
DT157	157	2.935	0.003	43.776
Total	382	4.200	0.001	373.000

The sample count and sample percentiles 5%, 50% (median), and 95% are compiled in Table 3 below by sub-study.

Table 3: Leak Rate Median, 5%, and 95% Percentiles by SoCalGas Sub-Study.

Sub-Study	N(count)	p5(scfh)	med(scfh)	p95(scfh)
3Dis_P1	56	0.030	0.940	22.290
3Dis_P2	32	0.057	1.224	36.362
AllDis_P1	78	0.007	0.231	9.192
AllDis_P2	59	0.016	0.321	9.697
DT157	157	0.042	1.350	9.990
Total	382	0.017	0.774	12.024

The same data but rolled-up by study (e.g., 3Dis_P1 and 3Dis_P2 grouped into one 3Dis study) is shown in Table 4 and 5.

Table 4: Leak Rate Mean, Minimum, and Maximum by Study.

Study	N(count)	mean(scfh)	min(scfh)	max(scfh)
3Dis	88	10.021	0.012	373.000
AllDis	137	1.911	0.001	54.811
DT157	157	2.935	0.003	43.776
Total	382	4.200	0.001	373.000

Table 5: Leak Rate Median, 5%, and 95% Percentiles by SoCalGas Study.

Study	N(count)	p5(scfh)	med(scfh)	p95(scfh)
3Dis	88	0.030	0.970	25.059
AllDis	137	0.007	0.273	9.192
DT157	157	0.042	1.350	9.990
Total	382	0.017	0.774	12.024

Data Analysis Using Dot Plots

The individual leak samples are plotted in a vertical dot plot and delineated by SoCalGas sub-study in Figure 2 and Figure 3. This type of plot is similar to a two-variable scatter plot, but, for the purposes of this analysis, the dot plots are used to visualize single variable trends of data. Most data for the three studies fall between 0.1 and 10 scfh.

Figure 2: Leak Rate Plot by Sample for Five SoCalGas Sub Studies.

Figure 3: Leak Rate Plot by Sample for Three SoCalGas Rolled Up Studies.

The summary tables and dot plots demonstrate excellent consistency between the Phase 1 and Phase 2 datasets for the 3-District and All District data sets when comparing generally across the range of leak rates encountered and the associated percentiles.

Data Analysis Using Box Plots

A box plot of the same leak data from the five sub-studies is shown in Figure 4 and by the rolled-up studies in Figure 5.

The box plot contains 50% of the data within the box, 25% above and 25% below the box. The median is drawn as a horizontal line within the box. Half of the data is above and below the median. The box tails (whiskers) extend up to the lesser of either the most extreme value or 1.5x the box height (also known as the inner quartile region, IQR).

Values outside the tails are known as outliers or extreme values (in general); however, this should not infer that there is something wrong with the data, rather a close look should be taken of these points. As both the vertical dot and box plots are using logarithmic scales for the y-axis (leak rate), one can see that the distribution of the data appears to be lognormally distributed as was the case in Phase 1. This will be confirmed in the next section of this report with a lognormal transformation and qualitative and quantitative statistical tests for lognormality.

Figure 4: Leak Rate Box Plots by SoCalGas Sub Studies.

Figure 5: Leak Rate Box Plots Rolled Up by SoCalGas Studies.

Data Transformation and Lognormality Checks

As was the case with the Phase 1 data, the log (base 10) of the leak rate is shown to be an appropriate transformation, and the combined SoCalGas data set was transformed to log(10) of the leak rate and plotted as a histogram distribution. A normal distribution fit is overlaid on the density plots and shows excellent agreement, see Figure 6.

Figure 6: Leak Rate Histogram of Log(10) of Combined SoCalGas Phase 1 and 2 Studies.

One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test for Lognormality

A Kolmogorov-Smirnov (KS) test for normality of the log(10) of leak rate was conducted on the combined Phase 1 and 2 data, see Table 6. For the Kolmogorov-Smirnov (K-S) test, a combined K-S p-value of greater than 0.05 for a one sample test of normality indicates there is no support that the distribution is not normally distributed.

The double negative is the "statistically preferred way" to state the relationship that the log transformed leak rate data is normally distributed as shown by its respective p-value being greater than 0.05.

Table 6: Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of Combined SoCal Gas Studies for Normality.

One-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test against theoretical distribution
normal((leakRateLog + 0.1889552) / 0.8748729)

Smaller group	D	P-value
leakRateLog:	0.0321	0.455
Cumulative:	-0.0471	0.183
Combined K-S:	0.0471	0.365

Quantile-Normal Plot Analysis of Lognormality

To visually check the transformation analysis, the quantile-normal plots of the log(10) transformed data were plotted for the combined Phase 1 and 2 data, see Figure 7. The plot shows that leak rate data from the combined data sets shows excellent conformance to a lognormal distribution. A theoretically perfect lognormal distribution is indicated by the overlaid straight line.

Figure 7: Quantile-Normal Plot of Log-normal Transformed Combined National Studies.

Methane Concentration vs. Leak Rate Analysis

The four leak concentration measurement categories are plotted side-by-side in Figure 8. The Decision Tree threshold (i.e., 10 scfh leak rate value) that separates "Not Large" from "Large" leak levels is plotted as a horizontal line. Each of the concentration levels that trigger a positive Decision Tree categorization are plotted as a vertical line at 80%, 20%, 60%, and 5% gas respectively. The zero values for concentration were set to 0.0001% gas for reference to be seen on the left-hand side of the x-axis log scale.

Figure 8: Separate Plots of Leak Concentrations vs. Rates by DT Category.

The upper left quadrants of the leak rate vs. concentration plots are the areas of false negatives for the DT process if each surface category was evaluated individually. One can visually see the very low number of false negatives (the measure of importance for the entire DT program) in these zones even when evaluated individually. This is the same as was seen in the Phase 1 data alone.

This portion of the DT process is an 'OR' gated approach (i.e., the DT will trigger an action if *any* one of the four category thresholds are met) which substantially reduces the number of false negatives from what is shown individually.

The above observations are also fully supported by the Bayesian probabilistic analysis later described in the next section of this report.

Probabilistic Decision Tree Error-Type Analysis

A non-parametric Bayesian probabilistic analysis was conducted on the Decision Tree predictive power. The output includes the expected fraction (or percent) of sites that have true/false negative/positive outcomes. The Bayesian proportional analysis provides the most likely value of the errors in a coherent manner, and additionally provides the upper and lower prediction limits around these values.

The results of the analysis are presented in Table 7 below and plotted in Figure 9 and Figure 10. The latter figure is a bar chart and additionally includes the error types for the Phase 1 data side-by-side with the combined Phase 1 & 2 data.

Table 7: Type I & II Decision Tree Errors with 5% and 95% Pred. Limits.

Error Type	Count	LPL%	MLV%	UPL%
False Neg	2	0.350	0.858	2.666
False Pos	129	81.218	86.577	90.423
True Neg	231	97.334	99.142	99.650
True Pos	20	9.577	13.423	18.782

Figure 9: Expected Decision Tree Output with Known DT Category.

Figure 10: Comparison of Phase 1 and Phase 1&2 Combined DT Performance.

The error data is very consistent between the Phase 1 data set and the combined data set. Both the true positive and true negative values increased and likewise both false positive and negative values decreased when the additional Phase 2 data was added to the Phase 1 data.

This trend demonstrates the decision tree is behaving as expected beyond its early development and implementation in Phase 1.

3-District Pilot Data Example

With the DT threshold set at the 10 scfh level, the Pilot study had a total number of 721 leaks with surface concentration measurements. Of these, the DT was triggered for measurement 111 times. Therefore, this relates to a flow rate measurement ratio of $111 / 721$ or 15.4%. In other words, when considering leak sites visited and screened with surface concentration measurements that one would expect leaks triggered by the DT process and criteria to have a less than 1 in 6 chance of being classified as potential non-hazardous large leak, scheduled for leak rate measurement, or prioritized for repair.

Population Mean Leak Rate Analysis

Monte Carlo Analysis of Leak Rate Fit to Lognormal Distribution

The combined SoCalGas study samples were fit to a lognormal distribution as was done in Phase 1. This fitted distribution was then analyzed with a Monte Carlo analysis with samples from the distribution fit set to the original field sample size, and the number of sampling events set to 10,000 - the same as for the bootstrap resampling analysis presented in the next section of this report. The same population statistics were calculated as with the bootstrap analysis for comparison.

Log-Normal Distribution Fit and Monte Carlo Analysis

The lognormal distribution fit of the SoCalGas combined study leak rates is shown in Figure 11.

The black points are the 382 empirical data points from the Phase 1 and Phase 2 field samples.

The red line is the fit of a lognormal distribution with the two parameters noted on the plot.

Figure 11: Leak Rate Cumulative Fractions of Combined SoCalGas Studies and L-N Fit.

Bootstrap Analysis of Field Leak Rate Data

A non-parametric bootstrap analysis using resampling with replacement was conducted to establish the mean leak rates and a full set of mean percentiles of the combined SoCalGas studies.

This analysis includes the overall mean leak rate and the mean leak rates for actual leak situations less than 10 scfh and greater than or equal to 10 scfh. The resample *sample size* was set to the same size as the field sample size, and the *number* of resamples was set to 10,000.

The bootstrap (boot) mean leak rates and minimum and maximum *mean* leak rates from the bootstrap analysis are presented in Table 8. The table also includes the Monte Carlo analysis of the lognormal distribution fit (L-N Fit) of the sample leak rate distribution as discussed in the previous section of this report.

The bootstrap leak rates are used as part of the emission rate calculations and are robust against non-normally distributed data.

Bootstrap Means

Table 8: Leak Rate Bootstrap Means for Combined SoCalGas Data.

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Comb Boot	4.200	1.106	1.709	10.451
Comb L-N Fit	5.042	0.325	4.097	6.462
Comb Boot LT10	1.567	0.110	1.179	2.011
Comb L-N Fit L10	1.388	0.021	1.309	1.461
Comb Boot GE10	47.592	16.792	15.611	134.807
Comb L-N Fit GE10	41.672	3.322	32.316	55.934

Boot: Bootstrap with 10,000 resamples

L-N: Log-normal fit with Monte Carlo Simulation with 10,000 draws

L10: Leak rate is less than 10 scfh

GE10: Leak rate is greater than or equal to 10 scfh

Bootstrap Percentiles

The 5th through 95th percentiles for the mean leak rates are presented in Table 9 for the bootstrap analysis.

Table 9: Leak Rate (scfh) Percentiles of the Bootstrap Mean.

Pct	Comb	Comb LT10	Comb GE10	Comb LNFIT	Comb LNFit LT10	Comb LNFIT GE10
5	2.628	1.389	23.951	4.542	1.354	36.605
10	2.865	1.429	26.935	4.641	1.361	37.587
15	3.057	1.454	29.703	4.709	1.366	38.265
20	3.235	1.474	32.317	4.767	1.370	38.822
25	3.392	1.491	35.235	4.812	1.373	39.315
30	3.534	1.509	37.693	4.858	1.376	39.743
35	3.674	1.524	39.540	4.903	1.379	40.179
40	3.800	1.538	41.390	4.942	1.382	40.637
45	3.939	1.552	43.452	4.983	1.384	41.060
50	4.064	1.565	45.395	5.022	1.387	41.450
55	4.207	1.579	47.468	5.063	1.390	41.888
60	4.347	1.592	49.736	5.104	1.393	42.323
65	4.514	1.607	52.631	5.149	1.396	42.723
70	4.690	1.620	55.238	5.195	1.399	43.248
75	4.867	1.638	58.002	5.248	1.402	43.790
80	5.084	1.658	61.404	5.307	1.405	44.401
85	5.350	1.683	65.058	5.379	1.409	45.120
90	5.679	1.712	70.333	5.473	1.414	46.074
95	6.189	1.750	78.368	5.618	1.421	47.503

A summary box plot of the bootstrap 10,000 resamples (at the original sample sizes) from the field leak rate data, and the separate Monte Carlo simulations (also sampled at the original field sample size) from the fitted distribution is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Bootstrap Mean Leak Rate Box Plots of Field Data and Log-Normal Fit.

The lognormal (or other appropriate fit such as log-gamma) fit with a Monte Carlo analysis can therefore provide an alternative to the bootstrap resampling of the actual field leak rate data until a large enough sample size is available from the field to run the bootstrap analysis.

Once a significant bootstrap sample size is established, one could then shift to the results of that analysis vs. fitting the distribution and running a Monte Carlo analysis.

Both the Phase 1 and 2 sample sets contained enough samples to use the bootstrap-resampling analysis. The Monte Carlo analysis was conducted to allow comparison and to show what the bootstrap analysis would trend towards with larger samples assuming no major shift in the distribution shape with further sampling.

Company Specific Emission Factor

With the information assembled in the previous sections, the SoCalGas-specific non-hazardous leak emission factor was updated based on the newly combined Phase 1 and 2 data sets.

Summary of EF (CH₄) Calculation Input Information

As completed in Phase 1, the following input information is used for the EF calculations.

The input values are used at three decimal places to prevent round-off errors in subsequent EF calculations which are rounded back to the supported number of significant digits:

1. Use the bootstraps of the mean leak rates from the SoCalGas combined study, for the:
 1. Entire sample set (**ALL**): 4.200 scfh
 2. Samples < 10 scfh (**L10**): 1.567 scfh
 3. Samples ≥ 10 scfh (**GE10**): 47.592 scfh
2. Use the Bayesian Error Table most likely value (MLV) proportions for true and false negatives and positives from the combined study:
 1. False Positives (**FP**): 86.577%
 2. True Positives (**TP**): 13.423%
 3. False Negatives (**FN**): 0.858%
 4. True Negatives (**TN**): 99.142%

Calculation of Distinct Emission Factors (CH₄)

The emission factors are calculated by properly combining the information above for two situations, when the Decision Tree criteria is met (predicting greater than or equal to 10 scfh leak rates) and when it is not met (predicting less than 10 scfh leak rates) as follows:

1. For DT met (**≥ 10 scfh** prediction):
$$= [\text{True Positive MLV\% (TP)}] \times [\text{Mean Leak Rate for } \geq 10 \text{ scfh (GE10)}] +$$
$$[\text{False Positive MLV\% (FP)}] \times [\text{Mean Leak Rate for } < 10 \text{ scfh (L10)}]$$
$$= 13.423/100 \times 47.592 \text{ scfh} + 86.577/100 \times 1.567 \text{ scfh}$$
$$= \mathbf{7.75 \text{ scfh}}$$
2. For DT not met (**< 10 scfh** prediction):
$$= [\text{True Negative MLV\% (TN)}] \times [\text{Mean Leak Rate for } < 10 \text{ scfh (L10)}] +$$
$$[\text{False Negative MLV\% (FN)}] \times [\text{Mean Leak Rate for } \geq 10 \text{ scfh (GE10)}]$$
$$= 99.142 / 100 \times 1.567 \text{ scfh} + 0.858 / 100 \times 47.592 \text{ scfh}$$
$$= \mathbf{1.96 \text{ scfh}}$$
3. If no concentration measurements were taken (i.e., no application of Decision Tree or leak rate measurements) then one should use the entire sample set bootstrap mean:
$$= \mathbf{4.22 \text{ scfh}}$$
4. If one has an actual leak rate measurement, then use that measurement.

Table of Emission Factors and Comparison to Phase 1 Values

The updated SoCalGas-specific emission factors calculated above using the combined Phase 1 and 2 data are summarized in Table 10 below.

Table 10: Table of SoCalGas Company Specific Emission Factors by DT Grouping.

EF Category	EF (scfh)
Combined All Case Ave EF	4.22
DT Not Triggered Ave EF	1.96
DT Triggered Ave EF	7.75

These DT related emission factors are conservative due to the nature of properly accounting for false negatives.

The Phase 1 and Phase 2 emission factors are plotted side-by-side in Figure 13. The two sets of values show excellent correlation and a slight refinement based on the additional random samples added into the calculation from the Phase 2 effort.

Figure 13: Phase 1 and Phase 1 & 2 Combined Emission Factors (CH₄).

Scenarios of Natural Gas (NG) EF Application

The scenarios that could be encountered in the field for leak repair are listed below in Table 11, with the guidance on what emission factor to use and when to use them. **Note that the emission factors in this table have been converted to natural gas using a methane composition of 93.4%.**

Table 11: Table of NG Emission Factors to use for Field Situations.

Situation Number	Field Situation Description	Emission Factor	
1	Measured concentration triggers DT < 10 scfh category & leak rate is not measured (which would be the typical situation) - Use DT Not Triggered Ave EF	2.099 scfh	0.050 Mscf/day
2	Measured concentration DT ≥ 10 category & leak rate is not measured (used when leak rate cannot be measured, such as leaks quickly repaired or when leak is in a remote location) - Use DT Triggered Ave EF	8.298 scfh	0.199 Mscf/day
3	Leak repaired and no concentration or leak rate measurements - Use Combined All Case Ave EF	4.518 scfh	0.108 Mscf/day
4	Measured concentration(s) trigger DT >10 category & then leak rate measured and actual leak rate is < 10 scfh - Use the actual leak rate measurement for the emission factor	Use actual leak rate measurement	Convert actual leak rate measurement
5	Measured concentration(s) trigger DT >10 category & then leak rate measured and actual leak rate is ≥ 10 scfh - Use the actual leak rate measurement for the emission factor	Use actual leak rate measurement	Convert actual leak rate measurement

Summary and Conclusions

SoCalGas collected additional field data to refine and improve the previously reported study of underground pipeline leaks to calculate SoCalGas company-specific natural gas emission factors for buried distribution system non-hazardous leaks.

With the additional data from Phase 2, the previously developed Decision Tree approach of using concentration measurements with thresholds to establish large and non-large, non-hazardous leaks saw an improvement in the true/false positive/negative values. For example, the true negative value increased from 98.9% to 99.1% while the false positive rate saw a decrease from 89.7% to 86.6%. This trend demonstrates an improvement in Decision Tree methodology's leak classification rate.

The size of the data set used for calculating weighted emission factors for large and non-large, non-hazardous leaks was increased by approximately 31%, but only accounted for a 2-5% change in the previously calculated emission factors (e.g., 4.30 SCFH to 4.22 SCFH for the DT Unknown category). This illustrates the reliability of the resulting SoCalGas emission factors, providing confidence that any additional data samples collected will continue to trend in the same direction.

The Decision Tree process allows for the assignment of appropriate emission factors for all non-large leaks where leak flow rate measurements are not performed as well as any Decision Tree-classified large leaks where leak flow rate measurements are not performed. This is particularly advantageous for Hazardous leaks that are classified based on the methane concentration data and repaired promptly at the time of detection removing the opportunity for leak flow measurement.

Appendix A: Phase 1 and 2 Leak Rate and Methane Concentration Data

For the SoCalGas studies, the DT approach collected methane concentration measurements at defined types of surface condition locations. The raw data containing the four defined types of surface concentration measurements and associated leak flow rates are listed in the Table 12 below and use the following abbreviations:

- Bar Hole (leak survey type) - BH
- Crack (or seam) In Pavement - CIP
- Small Sub-Structure (not gas system related) - SSS
- Unpaved Surface - US

Table 12: Leak Rate scfh Methane (CH₄) and Concentration (% gas) by Study.

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
1.	3Dis_P1	373.0000	100	.08	.	20
2.	3Dis_P1	172.4400	100	7	.	3
3.	3Dis_P1	22.2900	100	.7	.	5
4.	3Dis_P1	10.0000	100	1	.	2
5.	3Dis_P1	8.7500	100	.02	.0006	.08
6.	3Dis_P1	7.0600	85	.0153	0	.44
7.	3Dis_P1	6.9300	42	.8	0	9
8.	3Dis_P1	6.5500	10	.0357	.	10
9.	3Dis_P1	5.5400	.0004	.0044	0	.0072
10.	3Dis_P1	5.2900	5	.0285	.	5
11.	3Dis_P1	4.5300	30	.0015	0	30
12.	3Dis_P1	4.4400	12	.01	.	9
13.	3Dis_P1	4.0600	100	4	0	0
14.	3Dis_P1	3.8200	.2	.	.	.045
15.	3Dis_P1	3.6700	100	5	1	2
16.	3Dis_P1	3.2000	7	.4	.	.02
17.	3Dis_P1	3.1200	62	.3	.	.1
18.	3Dis_P1	2.2960	27	.1	.	23
19.	3Dis_P1	2.2300	100	6	.	0
20.	3Dis_P1	2.1800	100	1.5	.	2.5
21.	3Dis_P1	1.8400	25	.0923	.	.35
22.	3Dis_P1	1.2400	100	.	.	15
23.	3Dis_P1	1.2400	20	1	0	12
24.	3Dis_P1	1.1100	67	1.5	.	9.5
25.	3Dis_P1	1.1000	25	.02	.4	12
26.	3Dis_P1	1.0200	17	0	.17	12
27.	3Dis_P1	0.9800	25	.025	3	.03
28.	3Dis_P1	0.9600	.	.	64	.
29.	3Dis_P1	0.9200	48	.0073	0	.0237
30.	3Dis_P1	0.9100	85	.	.	.
31.	3Dis_P1	0.6900	0	0	100	0
32.	3Dis_P1	0.6100	25	.1	.	.1
33.	3Dis_P1	0.6100	0	0	10	0
34.	3Dis_P1	0.5700	30	.0145	0	.11
35.	3Dis_P1	0.5300	0	0	7.5	0
36.	3Dis_P1	0.4800	35	35	0	.

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
37.	3Dis_P1	0.4400	92	1	.0008	1
38.	3Dis_P1	0.3700	20	15	.03	5
39.	3Dis_P1	0.3300	70	0	0	10
40.	3Dis_P1	0.3300	.	.1	0	0
41.	3Dis_P1	0.2700	.	8	.	31
42.	3Dis_P1	0.2400	22	.01	.	.6
43.	3Dis_P1	0.2100	85	.15	.33	.
44.	3Dis_P1	0.1400	80	.002	0	0
45.	3Dis_P1	0.1200	70	50	7	25
46.	3Dis_P1	0.1115	89	.0148	.	1
47.	3Dis_P1	0.1100	0	0	0	70
48.	3Dis_P1	0.1100	80	0	0	80
49.	3Dis_P1	0.0830	52	0	0	26
50.	3Dis_P1	0.0600	.087	.032	0	.016
51.	3Dis_P1	0.0500	10	1.5	.001	.0015
52.	3Dis_P1	0.0400	.24	.045	.	.021
53.	3Dis_P1	0.0300	19	.0204	0	.375
54.	3Dis_P1	0.0300	2	.0525	.61	.152
55.	3Dis_P1	0.0200	4	.0003	0	.135
56.	3Dis_P1	0.0200	.	0	.03	.
57.	3Dis_P2	60.4315	82	82	.	0
58.	3Dis_P2	36.3620	86	.3245	.0815	.2017
59.	3Dis_P2	25.0592	60	.	94	70
60.	3Dis_P2	18.0900	.	100	.	2
61.	3Dis_P2	18.0700	95	.0105	0	.4785
62.	3Dis_P2	10.3981	100	.0208	0	.0706
63.	3Dis_P2	9.3400	100	.0101	.0004	.0775
64.	3Dis_P2	5.4000	90	0	.0068	.3
65.	3Dis_P2	4.2900	100	.5	.	.002
66.	3Dis_P2	4.1700	90	.1138	.	.4834
67.	3Dis_P2	3.4400	100	.0005	.	.0004
68.	3Dis_P2	2.8400	2	25	.	.79
69.	3Dis_P2	2.7500	100	.0048	.	.22
70.	3Dis_P2	2.3200	1.1	.66	.6	.095
71.	3Dis_P2	1.8400	68	.	.	20
72.	3Dis_P2	1.2672	64	.	.	22
73.	3Dis_P2	1.1800	60	.	.	4
74.	3Dis_P2	0.8264	65	.2	.0008	.0051
75.	3Dis_P2	0.8000	30	.	.	30
76.	3Dis_P2	0.6890	7	.0027	.0018	11
77.	3Dis_P2	0.4100	71	.1287	.	.0723
78.	3Dis_P2	0.4000	20	59	.02	7
79.	3Dis_P2	0.4000	.0182	.0008	.001	.0083
80.	3Dis_P2	0.3600	100	.195	.	.
81.	3Dis_P2	0.3500	.17	.	.	.04
82.	3Dis_P2	0.3176	100	.0333	0	.0017
83.	3Dis_P2	0.2500	15	5	.001	5
84.	3Dis_P2	0.2200	.1	.	.	.053
85.	3Dis_P2	0.0950	64	.062	.	4
86.	3Dis_P2	0.0770	.	1	.	.
87.	3Dis_P2	0.0567	100	.015	.0039	.0414
88.	3Dis_P2	0.0120	7	.09	.	.
89.	AllDis_P1	27.0447	.	40	.	20
90.	AllDis_P1	15.2524	.	0	.8	.015
91.	AllDis_P1	12.0244	.	8	.	1
92.	AllDis_P1	9.1915	.	.1	.1	1.45
93.	AllDis_P1	7.3507	23	0	.	.7

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
94.	AllDis_P1	5.2750	.	0	0	2
95.	AllDis_P1	5.2590	.	0	1.2	0
96.	AllDis_P1	5.1560	.	1	.	4
97.	AllDis_P1	4.2127	.	1	4	.1
98.	AllDis_P1	4.1216	.01	0	.	.05
99.	AllDis_P1	2.9205	0	0	.18	.35
100.	AllDis_P1	2.3995	.	2.95	0	.0103
101.	AllDis_P1	2.2184	0	0	0	.45
102.	AllDis_P1	1.9275	.	1.6	0	.17
103.	AllDis_P1	1.7470	.	0	.2	.13
104.	AllDis_P1	1.6990	.	0	10	0
105.	AllDis_P1	1.5844	.	.02	0	.97
106.	AllDis_P1	1.3139	.	0	0	1
107.	AllDis_P1	0.7927	.	.1	.	0
108.	AllDis_P1	0.7688	.	7.5	0	0
109.	AllDis_P1	0.7387	.	.03	.012	.2
110.	AllDis_P1	0.6676	.	3	0	.
111.	AllDis_P1	0.5958	.	0	40	0
112.	AllDis_P1	0.5698	.	.005	.06	0
113.	AllDis_P1	0.5600	.	0	0	.34
114.	AllDis_P1	0.4975	.	0	0	.3
115.	AllDis_P1	0.4060	.85	.06	0	.06
116.	AllDis_P1	0.4060	.	.01	0	3.5
117.	AllDis_P1	0.3879	.	.2	0	0
118.	AllDis_P1	0.3319	.	1	0	.0175
119.	AllDis_P1	0.3168	.	.3	.2	.72
120.	AllDis_P1	0.3120	2	.0007	.0002	.01
121.	AllDis_P1	0.2920	.	.3	0	.01
122.	AllDis_P1	0.2867	42	.02	0	0
123.	AllDis_P1	0.2823	.	.15	1.6	.0074
124.	AllDis_P1	0.2749	0	0	0	1.3
125.	AllDis_P1	0.2730	.	0	.	.03
126.	AllDis_P1	0.2710	.	.2	0	.2
127.	AllDis_P1	0.2367	.	0	0	.06
128.	AllDis_P1	0.2263	.	0	0	.04
129.	AllDis_P1	0.2170	.	0	0	.26
130.	AllDis_P1	0.1991	25	.0095	.	0
131.	AllDis_P1	0.1894	.	.06	.2	.11
132.	AllDis_P1	0.1884	.	0	0	0
133.	AllDis_P1	0.1726	.	0	0	.125
134.	AllDis_P1	0.1540	.	0	.23	0
135.	AllDis_P1	0.1465	.	.28	0	0
136.	AllDis_P1	0.1442	.	.002	.057	0
137.	AllDis_P1	0.1329	.	0	0	.04
138.	AllDis_P1	0.1147	1.2	.003	.005	.18
139.	AllDis_P1	0.1101	.	0	.02	0
140.	AllDis_P1	0.0964	.	.2	0	.
141.	AllDis_P1	0.0798	0	0	0	.05
142.	AllDis_P1	0.0769	0	0	.7	0
143.	AllDis_P1	0.0765	.	0	0	.2
144.	AllDis_P1	0.0625	.06	0	0	.003
145.	AllDis_P1	0.0614	.	0	.5	0
146.	AllDis_P1	0.0575	.	.05	.	.5
147.	AllDis_P1	0.0409	.02	0	0	0
148.	AllDis_P1	0.0403	.15	0	0	0
149.	AllDis_P1	0.0390	.004	.002	0	.04
150.	AllDis_P1	0.0358	.003	0	.	.3

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
151.	AllDis_P1	0.0319	.	1.6	.04	0
152.	AllDis_P1	0.0300	0	.028	0	0
153.	AllDis_P1	0.0273	.	.02	0	.005
154.	AllDis_P1	0.0220	.	.09	0	0
155.	AllDis_P1	0.0199	.	0	.07	0
156.	AllDis_P1	0.0179	.5	0	0	0
157.	AllDis_P1	0.0139	0	0	.015	0
158.	AllDis_P1	0.0136	.	.23	0	0
159.	AllDis_P1	0.0124	.	.005	0	0
160.	AllDis_P1	0.0107	.	.001	.	.0078
161.	AllDis_P1	0.0089	.	.07	0	.05
162.	AllDis_P1	0.0073	.01	0	.4	0
163.	AllDis_P1	0.0068	.	.17	.	0
164.	AllDis_P1	0.0055	.	0	.29	0
165.	AllDis_P1	0.0047	.	0	.	0
166.	AllDis_P1	0.0027	.	0	.1	0
167.	AllDis_P2	54.8114	18	7	4	9
168.	AllDis_P2	14.1489	10	0	0	10
169.	AllDis_P2	9.6973	100	0	1	4.5
170.	AllDis_P2	7.6688	100	0	.5	.7
171.	AllDis_P2	5.0709	100	.	.08	.08
172.	AllDis_P2	4.8828	.97	.23	.3	.3
173.	AllDis_P2	4.4625	2.3	.8	2	2
174.	AllDis_P2	4.3807	6	.005	.005	1
175.	AllDis_P2	3.3312	100	1	.0046	.18
176.	AllDis_P2	3.2666	.	1.5	.014	0
177.	AllDis_P2	2.9781	6	.1	2.2	.55
178.	AllDis_P2	2.3026	52	2	.6	.3
179.	AllDis_P2	2.0289	1.8	0	100	.2
180.	AllDis_P2	1.9204	.	4.5	14	.005
181.	AllDis_P2	1.9072	100	0	0	2.5
182.	AllDis_P2	1.7395	6	0	40	.2
183.	AllDis_P2	1.3429	.18	1	.	.2
184.	AllDis_P2	1.2784	100	.09	.002	.002
185.	AllDis_P2	1.1046	20	.01	0	.5
186.	AllDis_P2	1.0022	100	.09	.	1.4
187.	AllDis_P2	0.9336	.013	.03	1.5	.02
188.	AllDis_P2	0.7630	1.6	.2	.	0
189.	AllDis_P2	0.7500	.06	0	.007	.004
190.	AllDis_P2	0.7469	.5	.28	5.5	1
191.	AllDis_P2	0.6278	.35	0	0	.25
192.	AllDis_P2	0.5479	.	.23	2.4	.009
193.	AllDis_P2	0.4857	.37	0	.	.5
194.	AllDis_P2	0.4146	.	10	0	0
195.	AllDis_P2	0.4023	.	0	20	.
196.	AllDis_P2	0.3211	.	.1	.	.
197.	AllDis_P2	0.2877	.	.1	0	.17
198.	AllDis_P2	0.2808	6.5	.03	.	.
199.	AllDis_P2	0.2700	3.5	.0005	.0005	.3
200.	AllDis_P2	0.2621	6	.01	0	1
201.	AllDis_P2	0.2502	12	.15	0	0
202.	AllDis_P2	0.2307	1.5	.	7	.05
203.	AllDis_P2	0.2298	0	.5	0	.04
204.	AllDis_P2	0.2230	40	0	.0016	.2
205.	AllDis_P2	0.2220	2	.015	.	.0003
206.	AllDis_P2	0.1985	40	.005	0	.02
207.	AllDis_P2	0.1737	.	.02	2	.

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
208.	AllDis_P2	0.1440	1.5	.03	.0005	.3
209.	AllDis_P2	0.1406	4	.01	.	0
210.	AllDis_P2	0.1046	.45	0	0	.05
211.	AllDis_P2	0.0985	.15	.002	.	.001
212.	AllDis_P2	0.0687	.14	.02	0	.02
213.	AllDis_P2	0.0651	.	1	0	.0003
214.	AllDis_P2	0.0636	.035	0	0	.012
215.	AllDis_P2	0.0546	.02	.	.	.02
216.	AllDis_P2	0.0484	.	.025	.	0
217.	AllDis_P2	0.0475	0	0	0	.05
218.	AllDis_P2	0.0401	.7	.	0	0
219.	AllDis_P2	0.0276	.	.25	0	.007
220.	AllDis_P2	0.0173	2	2	.0005	.
221.	AllDis_P2	0.0171	.08	.	.025	.02
222.	AllDis_P2	0.0161	.	.05	0	0
223.	AllDis_P2	0.0156	.6	0	.	.
224.	AllDis_P2	0.0064	.	.035	0	0
225.	AllDis_P2	0.0008	.	.003	.022	0
226.	DT157	43.7760	.	.	.	100
227.	DT157	41.7180	.	.	100	.
228.	DT157	20.0870	100	100	.	.
229.	DT157	19.4700	.	.	.	16
230.	DT157	18.2144	.	40	100	2
231.	DT157	15.6582	100	.	18	8
232.	DT157	12.2475	.	2	100	.
233.	DT157	9.9900	.	.	90	.
234.	DT157	9.5397	100	.	.	2
235.	DT157	9.5040	.	8	100	.
236.	DT157	9.1800	95	.	.	.
237.	DT157	7.6152	.	5	100	.
238.	DT157	7.5300	.	23	100	.
239.	DT157	6.6519	.	3	.	12
240.	DT157	6.3480	.	.	.	2.5
241.	DT157	6.2496	.	3	.	8
242.	DT157	6.1970	.	.	.	8.5
243.	DT157	6.0848	.	.	.	50
244.	DT157	5.9664	100	.5	.	.
245.	DT157	5.7782	.	.	62	4
246.	DT157	5.1899	.	.	.	9
247.	DT157	4.8633	.	32	.	.
248.	DT157	4.8165	.	.	100	7
249.	DT157	4.7489	.	13	.	.
250.	DT157	4.4340	29	.	.	.6
251.	DT157	4.3662	.	.	100	10
252.	DT157	4.1681	.	10	.	3
253.	DT157	4.0392	.	100	100	.
254.	DT157	3.9882	.	80	.	100
255.	DT157	3.8766	30	.	100	.
256.	DT157	3.7304	20	.	.	.
257.	DT157	3.6167	100	.	100	.
258.	DT157	3.5326	.	.	.	5.6
259.	DT157	3.2760	.	.	.	20
260.	DT157	3.2640	.	41	48	.
261.	DT157	3.2550	.	5	16	1.5
262.	DT157	3.2484	.	9	.	10
263.	DT157	3.0195	.	8	100	.
264.	DT157	2.9820	.	.	100	.

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
265.	DT157	2.8928	.	.	.	14
266.	DT157	2.7444	.	.	100	.
267.	DT157	2.6745	.	.	.	1.1
268.	DT157	2.5850	.	.	50	.
269.	DT157	2.5837	.	1.3	.	.
270.	DT157	2.5560	.	.	.	40
271.	DT157	2.5212	100	.	100	.
272.	DT157	2.5164	.	20	.	18
273.	DT157	2.4960	.	.	100	.
274.	DT157	2.2884	100	20	.	.
275.	DT157	2.1470	.	.	100	.
276.	DT157	2.1249	10	.	.	50
277.	DT157	2.1040	.	.	.	1.5
278.	DT157	2.0911	.	.	8	.
279.	DT157	2.0910	.	.	72	3
280.	DT157	2.0598	.	20	100	.
281.	DT157	1.9665	.	100	.	.
282.	DT157	1.9344	.	.	58	.
283.	DT157	1.8764	.	.	3.5	.
284.	DT157	1.8600	.	.	.	2
285.	DT157	1.8368	.	.	100	.
286.	DT157	1.7481	52	.	22	.5
287.	DT157	1.7305	.	.	.	100
288.	DT157	1.7206	.	2.5	.	.
289.	DT157	1.7202	.	.	.	1.6
290.	DT157	1.6632	.	.	.	80
291.	DT157	1.6414	23	.	.	.
292.	DT157	1.6083	.	.	40	.
293.	DT157	1.5748
294.	DT157	1.5258	.	.	.	1.7
295.	DT157	1.5210	.	4	35	6
296.	DT157	1.4997	22	5	.	.
297.	DT157	1.4855	.	10	.	.
298.	DT157	1.4640	.	.	.	2.5
299.	DT157	1.4552	.	2	26	.
300.	DT157	1.4472	.	.	59	.
301.	DT157	1.4310	.	.	.	6
302.	DT157	1.3986	100	.	.	.
303.	DT157	1.3860	.	.	100	.
304.	DT157	1.3500	.	.	.	1.14
305.	DT157	1.3392	.	.	100	.
306.	DT157	1.2760	.	75	.	.
307.	DT157	1.2619
308.	DT157	1.2204	.	.	.	15
309.	DT157	1.1704	.	.	100	.
310.	DT157	1.1678	.	.6	.	6
311.	DT157	1.1464	.	1.45	.	1.23
312.	DT157	1.13642
313.	DT157	1.1046	100	.	35	.
314.	DT157	1.0860	.	.	100	.2
315.	DT157	1.0416	70	.	.	.
316.	DT157	1.0130	20	.	.	.
317.	DT157	0.9859	.	.	100	.
318.	DT157	0.9558	.	.	.	40
319.	DT157	0.9169	.	3.7	.	.
320.	DT157	0.9130	.	.	.	1
321.	DT157	0.8978	.	.	.	9

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
322.	DT157	0.8960	.	.	52	.
323.	DT157	0.8245	.	6	.	1.4
324.	DT157	0.8190	.	.	.	13
325.	DT157	0.8160	.	23	.	.
326.	DT157	0.7801	.	.	7	.
327.	DT157	0.7788	.	.	.	35
328.	DT157	0.7686	.	.	100	.
329.	DT157	0.7680	.	.	100	.
330.	DT157	0.7466	.	20	.	.
331.	DT157	0.7068	.	.	.	2.6
332.	DT157	0.7068	.	.	88	.
333.	DT157	0.6868
334.	DT157	0.6696	.	.	84	.
335.	DT157	0.6426	.	.	65	.
336.	DT157	0.6210
337.	DT157	0.60307
338.	DT157	0.5940	.	.	.	5
339.	DT157	0.5346	.	32	.	.
340.	DT157	0.5173	.	.	.	1.7
341.	DT157	0.4980	.	.	.	1.5
342.	DT157	0.4934
343.	DT157	0.4809	18	.	.	.
344.	DT157	0.4800	.	25	.	.
345.	DT157	0.4608	.	.	.	1
346.	DT157	0.4406	.	40	.	.14
347.	DT157	0.4158	.	.	.	2.6
348.	DT157	0.3845	.	3	.	.
349.	DT157	0.3674
350.	DT157	0.3302	.	6	.	.
351.	DT157	0.3294	.	.	63	.
352.	DT157	0.3206	.	.	.	4.4
353.	DT157	0.3201
354.	DT157	0.3124	25	.	.	.
355.	DT157	0.3121	.	.61	.	.
356.	DT157	0.3009	.	.	1.1	.
357.	DT157	0.2928	.	20	.	.
358.	DT157	0.2646	.	.	.	1
359.	DT157	0.2598	.9	.	.	.
360.	DT157	0.2394	.	2	.	16
361.	DT157	0.2325	.	.	20	.
362.	DT157	0.2317	.	.	.	5
363.	DT157	0.1844	24	.	.	.
364.	DT157	0.1640	.	1.6	.	.
365.	DT157	0.156012
366.	DT157	0.1558	.	.	32	.
367.	DT157	0.1512	.	6	.	.
368.	DT157	0.0991	.	1	10	.
369.	DT157	0.0857	.5	.	.	.
370.	DT157	0.073013
371.	DT157	0.0471	.	1.08	.	.078
372.	DT157	0.0456	.	.	.4	.
373.	DT157	0.0456	.	.	13	.
374.	DT157	0.0444	.	.	32	.
375.	DT157	0.0420	.	1.12	.	.
376.	DT157	0.0342	.	.	100	.
377.	DT157	0.0337
378.	DT157	0.0329	1	.	.	.

	Study	Leak Rate (scfh)	Conc. BH (% gas)	Conc. CIP (% gas)	Conc. SSS (% gas)	Conc. US (% gas)
379.	DT157	0.0173008
380.	DT157	0.0158	.	.15	.	.
381.	DT157	0.0037	.	.	.4	.
382.	DT157	0.0030	.	.034	.	.

References

1. Ersoy, D., Newton E, Powell J, Bong G, Wiley K, *2019 Emission Factor Pilot Study*. 2020, Gas Technology Institute: United States.

End of Phase 2 Report